

Study of Risk Factors and Management of Cellulitis in Lower Limb in Jharkhand Population

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Abstract:

Background: Cellulitis is an acute bacterial infection of the dermis and associated with subcutaneous tissue. It is difficult to diagnose because there are no exact criteria or any specific blood culture for cellulitis. Hence diagnosing and treating cellulitis is a clinical challenge for surgery.

Method: 85 adult patients were studied with demographic data. Blood examination included RBS, CBC, LFT, RFT, urine culture and sensitivity, and microbiological profile. Radiologically, chest X-ray, USG abdomen + pelvis, local USG with colour Doppler X-ray of the affected limb, and CECT. Vital signs of every patient were noted. Initially treated with conservative treatment, if not responded to conservative treatment, surgical approach was carried out with fasciotomy with debridement.

Results: 42 (49%) were treated conservatively, and 43 (50.5%) with surgical intervention; risk factors were 41 (48.2%), 30 (35.2%) toe with web infection, 7 (8.2%) venous insufficiency, 6 (7%) diabetic, 1 (1.1%) chronic lymphedemous, and 79 (92%) had good results, and 4 (4.7%) had poor skin grafting, and 2 (2.3%) patients expired.

Conclusion: The cellulitis of the lower limb in diabetic patients had the most common risk factors. Appropriate conservative treatment and emergency surgical intervention with hospital admission. Treating with culture-directed antibiotics can prevent morbidity and mortality.

Keywords: Conservative, Cellulites, Fasciotomy, Debridement, Skin graft, Vital signs.

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Introduction

Streptococci most often cause cellulitis, a skin and soft tissue infection. It is characterized by inflammatory signs such as pain, swelling, redness, and warmth of the affected area and/or systemic signs of malaise, fever, nausea, or vomiting. Cellulitis affects the lower limb in 88% of cases [1]. Delay in treatment could lead to life-threatening and debilitating complications such as necrotizing hypodermatitis, necrotizing fasciitis, abscess formation, septic shock, and even death in extreme cases.

Cellulitis is an acute bacterial infection of the dermis and associated subcutaneous tissue, with 60% of cases affecting the lower limb [2]. Erysipelas is a form of cellulitis that presents with more marked superficial inflammation. The diagnosis of cellulitis can be challenging because many patients who present with suspected lower limb cellulitis require emergency treatment subsequently diagnosed other than cellulitis [3]. Routine hematological biochemical blood tests and blood cultures are not specific for cellulitis. This leads to unnecessary prescription

of antibiotics. Definitive diagnostic criteria could potentially improve clinical care [4]. Hence an attempt was made to evaluate the cellulitis with a hematological and bacteriological profile.

Material and Method

85 adult patients regularly visited the surgery department of Medinirai Medical College Daltonganj, Palamu (district), Jharkhand-822101 were studied.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients above 18 years with cellulitis of the lower limbs, either unilateral or bilateral, irrespective of etiology. The patients who gave their consent for the study were selected.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients below 18 years with cellulitis other than lower limb suffering with Hansen disease and patients presented with necrotizing fasciitis or deep-seated infections with ulcers over lower limbs were excluded from the study.

Method: Every patient's demographic data and past and present clinical history were recorded.

Blood examination included CBC, RBS, LFT, RFT, and urine culture sensitivity microbiological profile, which was studied. Patients were examined for routine radiographic (chest X-ray, USG abdomen + pelvis, local USG with color Doppler, X-ray of affected limb CECT). Anemia and jaundice during clinical examination, notes on hydration and nutrition were noted, respiratory and cardiac examination. Every patient's vital signs, viz. temperature, blood pressure, respiratory rate, and pulse rate, were recorded.

Initially every patient was managed with conservative treatment. When there was no response to conservative management, patients were treated with surgery in the form of subcutaneous release incisions. Fasciotomy with debridement was done for patients who progressed to necrotizing fasciitis.

Most patients lose their protective skin barrier, making them more dehydration resistant. To prevent skin maceration, the wounds were dressed and the patient's hydration status was corrected. When

a patient had advanced cellulitis characterized by devitalized, bronzy skin, underlying pus-pointing, and possible subcutaneous abscess, the skin is carefully debrided and any underlying abscess is evacuated. The surgical protocol involves making incisions both within and outside the devitalized skin region until the area of newly viable tissue is reached. Hemostasis was achieved, and the wounds were irrigated well. Adequate blood transfusions were used to treat blood loss during surgery. Split-thickness skin grafting is used when it is doubtful that the wound margins and those that leave raw regions will mend.

Duration of study was from March 2012 to October 2024.

Statistical Analysis: Demographic data of bacteriology were classified with percentage. Risk factors and duration of hospital stay were compared with p-value. The statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS software. The ratio of male and female was 2:1.

Figure 1: Debridement

Figure 2: Fasciotomy

Figure 3: Incision and Drainage

Figure 4: Split-Thickness Skin Grafts

Observation and Results

Table 1: Demographic data of the patients with lower limb cellulitis –

- A. **Bacteriology:** 24 (28.2%) had no growth, 16 (18.8%) had growth, 45 (52.9%) had pus sent for culture.
- B. **Risk factors:** 41 (48.2%) - had trauma, 30 (35.2%) had toe with web infection, 7 (8.2%) had venous insufficiency, 6 (7%) had diabetic mellitus, 1 (1.1%) had chronic lymph edema.
- C. Groups of management: 42 (49.4%) were conservative, 43 (50.5%) were surgical patients.
- D. Final outcome in two groups: 79 (92%) had good results, 4 (4.7%) had poor skin grafting, 2 (2.3%) patients expired.

Table 2: Study of Bacteriology: 45 (52.9%) pus sent for culture, 24 (28.2%) had no growth, 16 (18.8%) had growth, 1 (1.17%) had citrobacter, 3 (3.52%) coag -ve staph, 4 (4.7%) had coag +ve staph, 2 (2.3%) had E.Coli, 4 (4.7%) had klebsiella, 2 (2.3%) had pseudomonas.

Table 3: Comparison of risk factors in two groups of management –

- Trauma: 11 (26.1%) in conservative, 30 (69.7%) in surgical patients and $p < 0.001$ (p value is highly significant)
- Toe web infection: 24 (57.1%) in conservative, 6 (13%) and $p < 0.001$ (p value is highly significant).
- Venous insufficiency: 6 (13.9%) in surgical, 1 (2.3%) in conservative and $p < 0.001$ (p value is highly significant).
- Diabetic: 5 (11.9%) were conservative, 1 (2.3%) was surgical
- Chronic lymphoedema: 1 (2.3%) was conservative and zero in surgical $p < 0.001$ (p value is highly significant).

Table 4: Comparison of hospital stay in both group (days) 3-11 days in conservative group mean value 4.74 (± 1.82), 3-30 days 10.24 (± 5.84) mean value in surgical group $p < 0.001$ (p value is highly significant).

Table 1: Demographic data of the patients (No. of patients: 85)

A) Bacteriology	Number of patients	Percentage (%)
No growth	24	28.2
Growth	16	18.8
Pus sent for culture	45	52.9
B) Risk factors		
Trauma	41	48.2
Toe with web infection	30	35.2
Venous insufficiency	7	8.2
Diabetes	6	7
Chronic lymphedema	1	1.1
Total	85	100
Groups of management		
1) Conservative	42	49.4
2) Surgical	43	50.5
Total	85	99.9
Final outcome in two groups of management		
a) Good	79	92%
b) Poor skin	4	4.7
c) Expired	2	2.3
d) Total	85	100

Figure 5: Demographic data of the patients

Table 2: Study of Biocenology

Culture study	Number of patients (85)	Percentage (%)
Pus sent for culture	45	52.9
No growth	24	28.2
Growth	16	18.8
Citrobacter	1	1.17
Coag -ve staph	3	3.52
Coag +ve staph	4	4.7
E. coli	2	2.3
Klebesiella	4	4.7
Pseudomonas	2	2.3

Figure 6: Study of Biocenology

Table 3: Comparison of risk factors in two groups of management

Risk factors	Conservative (42)	Surgical (43)	p value
Trauma	11 (26.1%)	30 (69.7%)	P<0.001
Toe web infection	24 (57%)	6 (13%)	P<0.001
Venous insufficiency	1 (2.3%)	6 (13.9%)	P>0.202
Diabetes	5 (11.9%)	1 (2.3%)	p>0.42
Chronic lymphocdenous	1 (2.3%)	0	P<0.001

P<0.001 = p value is highly significant

Figure 7: Comparison of risk factors in two groups of management

Table 4: Comparison of hospital stays in both groups

Duration of hospital stay (days)	Conservative (42)	Surgical (43)	p value
Min – Max	3-11	3-30	P<0.001
Mean ±SD	4.74 (± 1.82)	10.24 (±5.84)	P<0.001

P<0.001 = p value is highly significant

Discussion

Present study of risk factors and management of cellulitis in lower limb. In demographic data out of 85 patients, 42 (49.4%) were conservative and 43 (50.5%) were surgical patients; 6 (7%) were diabetic, and 7 (8.25%) had venous insufficiency. The factors included 41 (82%) trauma and 30 (35.2%) toe with web infections. The final outcome included 79 (92%) who had good results, 4 (4.7%) who had poor skin grafting, and 2 (2.3%) patients who expired (table 1).

In a bacteriological profile, 45 (52.9%) patients pus was sent for culture. 24 (28.2%) had no growth, 16 (18.8%) had growth, 4 (4.7%) coag +ve staph and Klebsiella 3 (3.52%) coag -ve staph 2 (2.3%) pseudomonas (Table 2).

In the comparative study of the conservative and surgical groups in trauma study toe web infection, chronic lymphedema has a significant p-value (p <

0.001) (Table 3). In comparison, the hospital stay in both groups had significant value (p < 0.001) (Table 4) (Figure 1, 2, 3 and 4). These findings are more or less in agreement with previous studies [5,6,7]. 8.9% to 47.4% lower limb cellulitis included leg abscess, necrotizing fasciitis, bullae, hemorrhagic lesions, necrosis, skin abscess, phlebitis, and diabetic ketoacidosis; on the other hand, delay in nicotine addiction and delay in suitable antibiotic treatment, use of NSAID will enhance these complications [8]. A break in the physical barrier of the skin seems to be a major determinant for developing cellulitis. A bridge in the skin barrier serves as a potential portal of entry for cellulitis-causing pathogens.

In many cases, drugs contain potent corticosteroids, which cause skin atrophy, dyschromia, hypertrichosis, and striae in the long run. It results in fragile skin that is more susceptible to penetration and colonization by cellulitis-causing pathogens [9].

The general risk factor for lower limb cellulitis is obesity. Obesity-related immune system dysfunction with a decreased cell-mediated immune response could predispose obese individuals to developing cellulitis. Obesity also associated with other comorbid conditions like diabetic mellitus and hypertension, which may otherwise influence the risk for lower limb cellulitis [10]. Bony changes were observed in 12% of the patients with cellulitis of the concerned limb in the phalanges or metatarsals in patients with diabetes mellitus.

Summary and Conclusion

As the leg is the most common area of lower limb affected diseases, like venous ulcers, eczema, and lymphedema of the leg, must get treatment of these conditions as they predispose to cellulitis. Smoking and alcohol consumption will be the aggravating factors in cellulitis; moreover, diabetes mellitus increases the severity of cellulitis. The present study demands further nutritional, environmental, genetic, and pathophysiological studies because there is currently insufficient evidence available of diagnostic criteria or tools for confirmation of cellulitis in the lower limb.

Limitation of study: Owing to tertiary location of research centre, small number of patient's lack of latest techniques, we have limited finding and results.

This research work was approved by the ethical committee of Medinirai Medical College Daltaganj palamu (district) Jharkhand-822101.

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